

A Criterion for the Delamination of Composite Laminates

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Abstract

In this paper, the mixed-mode fracture criterion of the delamination onset of composite laminates was presented. Using this criterion, it is expected that the failures of various composite laminates whose major failure mode is delaminated can be analyzed.

1. Introduction

The delamination problem is one of the most important problems affecting the use of structural composite laminates. It is often encountered as the most damaging laminate failure mode. Therefore, many scholars did a lot study for it. Especially mentioned is the work Wang and his fellows did [1-6]. They considered that since the delamination cracking mechanism of composite laminates is essentially a fracture problem, a description of cracking process requires a fracture mechanics analysis. References [1,2] pointed out that the experiments and analyses had showed that the delamination onset loads of composite laminates are affected by ply thickness of composite laminates. This affect, if a stress criterion or a strain criterion is used to analyze the delamination problem, can not be considered, while if a fracture mechanics method, for example, an energy release rate criterion is used, can be considered. However, it is not satisfactory that the mixed-mode fracture criterion of the delamination onset of composite laminates is investigated. To this, it is supposed in almost all literatures that the delamination onset is matrix-delaminated. Moreover, it is also supposed that the energy release rate of the mixed-mode cracking actions is the sum of energy release rates G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} , i. e.

$$G = G_I + G_{II} + G_{III}$$

This formula is unreasonable based on the following results.

(I). Data obtained for bulk epoxy and epoxy adhesive under mode-I action ranged from 90 to 210J/m for G_{Ic} and a somewhat higher value for $G_{(I,II)c}$ under mixed-mode actions [7].

(II). In a comprehensive experimental correlation using a T300/934 graphite-epoxy system, Law [8] found $G_I \sim 230J/m$, and a somewhat lower value for mixed-mode $G_{(I,II)c}$.

(III). Recent experiments by Whlkin, et. al. [9] and Schapery, et. al [10] have re-

ported that value G_{Ic} can vary depending on the microscopic crack path. For example, Fig. 1 illustrates two situations where the crack opening is in mode - I, but the microscopic crack path in the two cases is different. For a graphite - epoxy system, the value G_{Ic} found for cracking path parallel to the fiber direction, as shown in Fig. 1(a) ranged from 90 to 140J/m, while for cracking path normal to the fiber, as shown in Fig. 1(b) ranged from 210 to 260J/m.

fig. 1. Mode - I Delamination Growth Direction; (a) In the Direction of the Reinforcing Fibers; (b) In the Direction Normal to the Reinforcing Fiber

(IV). The experimental results of mixed-mode matrix cracks of unidirectional composite laminates reported by Wang et. al. [11] showed the total $G_{(I,II)c}$ to increase with G_I / G_{II} . In other words, $G_{(I,II)c}$ is multi-valued; see, e. g. the curve shown in Fig. 2.

fig. 2. Critical Energy Release Rate for Mixed - Mode Delamination in Graphite - Epoxy Laminate. Ref. [11]

In this paper, therefore, the mixed-mode fracture criterion of the delamination onset of composite laminates was presented. Using this criterion, it is expected that the failures of various composite laminates whose major failure mode is delaminated can be analyzed.

2. The Mixed-mode Fracture Criterion of the Delamination Onset of Composite Laminates

Generally speaking, the delamination onset cracking of composite laminates is

mixed-mode. And its mixed-mode fracture parameter and its corresponding critical value(Fracture toughness value) are very complicated. Based on previous investigations [1-12] it can be imagined that the fracture toughness value of the delamination onset of composite laminates is affected by many factors, such as a matrix material, the ply thickness adjacent to the delamination initiation position, the cracking modes, etc. To determine this complex fracture toughness value to analyze the failures of various composite laminates whose major failure mode is delaminated, it is necessary that the experiments and analyses for representative specimens should be made and then the results of experiments and analyses should be universally treated with.

In an isotropic material , a mixed-mode fracture criterion can be expressed as

$$f(G_I, G_{II}, G_{III}, \theta, G_c) = 0$$

where G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} are the opening-mode , the shear-mode and the tearing-mode. energy release rates, respectively, θ is polar angle.

By means of the concept of the effective crack introduced by Wang[1], we will use the fracture mechanics method to investigate the delamination problem. The polar angle θ can not be considered here because the delamination growth is in the direction of the original delamination. Thus, the criterion of delamination growth can be expressed as

$$f(G_I, G_{II}, G_{III}, G_c) = 0 \tag{1}$$

If the energy release rate of delamination growth is assumed to be

$$G = (\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}})^m + (\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}})^n + (\frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIc}})^l \tag{2}$$

where G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and G_{IIIc} are opening-mode, the shear-mode and the tearing-mode fracture toughnesses, critical energy release rates, respectively, m , n and l material constants, a_c , then the mixed-mode fracture criterion of the delamination onset of composite laminates can be expressed as:

$$G(a_c) \geq 1 \tag{3}$$

where a_c is the effective crack length introduced by Wang[1] whose magnitude is above the ply thickness of composite laminates.

If the equality in the equation (3) is taken , the equation which is satisfied by G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} can be obtained by means of the equation(2):

$$(\frac{G_I(a_c)}{G_{Ic}})^m + (\frac{G_{II}(a_c)}{G_{IIc}})^n + (\frac{G_{III}(a_c)}{G_{IIIc}})^l = 1 \tag{4}$$

or

$$Y_c = G_{Ic}^m (a_c) + A G_{IIc}^n (a_c) + B G_{IIIc}^l (a_c) \tag{5}$$

where Y , A and B are all material constants:

$$Y_c = G_{Ic}^m, A = G_{Ic}^m \cdot G_{IIc}^{-n}, B = G_{Ic}^m \cdot G_{IIIc}^{-l} \tag{6}$$

The following fracture parameter is introduced:

$$Y = G_I^m + A G_{II}^n + B G_{III}^l \tag{7}$$

Thus, the delamination onset criterion of composite laminates can be expressed as:

$$Y(a_c) \geq Y_c \quad (8)$$

3. The Determination of the Fracture Parameter and Its Corresponding Critical Value

As mentioned above, the mixed-mode fracture parameter and the corresponding critical value of composite laminates are very complicated and it is necessary that the experiments and the analyses for a set of representative composite laminates whose major failure mode is delaminated should be made to determine these values. Specifically speaking, introduce the following function:

$$\omega = Y_c - (G_I^m + AG_{II}^n + BG_{III}^l) \quad (9)$$

Thus, based on the criterion presented in the previous section, ω must be equal to zero when the composite laminate is being delaminated. Thus, if we do the experiment and the analysis for a representative specimen, then a set of data, ω , $G_I(a_c)$ and $G_{II}(a_c)$ and $G_{III}(a_c)$ may be obtained. If we do the experiments and the analyses for k representative specimens, then k sets of data may be obtained. By means of the k sets of data and the equation (9), the constants Y_c , A , B , m , n and l may be determined by using the nonlinear curve fitting technique. Therefore, the mixed-mode fracture toughness value Y_c has been determined and the corresponding fracture parameter may be determined by the equation (7).

The experiments mentioned above pointed out that the relations between the uniformly produced strain ε and the delamination size a are measured for the composite laminates which can be simplified as the quasi-three dimension problem by means of nondestructive evaluation ultrasonic pulse-echo method or other methods. If the delamination onset law is merely explored, it is satisfactory that the uniformly produced strain ε_c corresponding to the effective crack a_c is measured. The analyses mentioned above pointed out that the quasi-three dimension finite element analyses for experimental specimens are made to determine the values, $G_I(a_c)$, $G_{II}(a_c)$ and $G_{III}(a_c)$. The representative specimens mentioned above can be referred to the reference [12].

4. An Example and discussions

Now we take some results of the reference [12] to illustrate the application of the mixed-mode delamination onset fracture criterion to the delamination problem of composite laminates.

T300/5208 graphite-epoxy composite laminates are as follows:

- A $[\pm 45/0/90]_s$
- B $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$
- C $[45/0/-45/90]_s$

The analyses for the three kinds of composite laminates showed that G is negligible [12]. Thus, the equation (5) can be simplified as:

$$Y_c = G_I^m(a_c) + (AG_{II}^n)(a_c) \quad (10)$$

Because there are only the three kinds of composite laminates and there are four constants to be determined in the equation (10), we suppose A to be one. Thus

$$Y_c = G_I^m(a_c) + G_{II}^n(a_c) \quad (11)$$

Energy release rates, G_I and G_{II} resulting from the uniformly produced strain $\varepsilon = 0.004$,

critical strain ϵ_c and the corresponding energy release rates, $G_I(a_c)$ and $G_{II}(a_c)$ are showed in the following table. Nonlinear equation sets of unknowns Y_c , m and n can be obtained by means of the data, $G_I(a_c)$ and $G_{II}(a_c)$, in the table, and the equation (11). Solving these equations, the values Y_c , m and n can be obtained.

What is required to be illustrated here is that the number of the representative composite laminates mentioned above is not less than six when G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} all exist. When this number is equal to six and G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} all exist, it is necessary that the values Y_c , A , B , m , n and l are determined not to use the nonlinear curve fitting technique but to solve the nonlinear equation sets, as did above.

Obviously, the correct prediction for the three kinds of composite laminates can be given by means of the found material constants, Y , m and n , and the mixed-mode fracture criterion of the delamination onset of composite laminates presented in this paper.

We randomly point out that if the mixed-mode fracture parameter under the mixed-mode cracking actions is supposed as the sum of single-mode fracture parameters, G_I and G_{II} , i. e.

$$G = G_I + G_{II} \quad (12)$$

obviously, the value G_c expected according to values, $G_I(a_c)$ and $G_{II}(a_c)$, in the table are different and are 82.9J/m, 100.9J/m and 92.8J/m, respectively, for the composite laminates, A, B and C.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the mixed-mode fracture criterion of the delamination onset of composite laminates was presented. Using this criterion, it is expected that the failures of various composite laminates whose major failure mode is delaminated can be analyzed.

Table of Energy Release Rates and Critical Uniform Strain

	$[\pm 45/0/90]_s$	$[0/\pm 45/90]_s$	$[\pm 45/0/-45/90]_s$
G1	51.7	17.0	32.2
G2	6.3	39.0	25.8
ϵ_c	0.00572	0.00721	0.00640
$G1(a_c)$	73.9	30.6	51.5
$G2(a_c)$	9.0	70.3	41.3

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